

Synthesis of 4[α,γ Diamino Butyric] and 5[α,γ Diamino Butyric] Oxytocin

M. A. EL-MAGHRABY

Chemistry Department, Faculty of Science, Assiut University, Assiut, Egypt, A R.E.

Manuscript received 30 January 1975 ; accepted 6 May 1976

4[α,γ diamino butyric] oxytocin, an analog of the neurohypophyseal hormone oxytocin in which the glutamine residue at position 4 is replaced by an α,γ diamino butyric, and 5[α,γ diamino butyric] oxytocin, an analog in which the asparagine residue at position 5 is replaced by an α,γ diamino butyric residue have been synthesized.

IN the course of the systematic study in several laboratories of the relation of the chemical structure to biological activity of peptide hormones, the role of the side chains of the glutamine and asparagine residues in position 4, and 5 of the peptide ring of oxytocin has been explored. From this work¹⁻³ it can be concluded that in general, position 5 of oxytocin exhibits a considerable tolerance to structural alterations with respect to oxytocin—like activities i.e. rat uterotonic, milk ejecting, and avian vasodepressor activities, less tolerance is exhibited with respect to vasopressin—like activities i.e. rat pressor and rat anti-diuretic activities.

The single deviation from this trend up to now was noted in studies of the biological properties of [4-glutamic acid] oxytocin, an analog bearing a carboxyl group in place of the carboxamide group in position 4. This analog exhibited only 1/1000 of the avian vasodepressor activity and approximately 1/300 of the rat uterotonic activity of oxytocin⁴.

In view of the latter findings, we became interested in evaluating the importance of the carboxamide moiety

of the glutamine residue for the manifestation of the biological properties of oxytocin. Therefore, 4[α,γ diamino butyric] oxytocin, an analog in which this carboxamide moiety of glutamine is formally replaced by a amino moiety has been synthesized. Moreover, in continued effort to analyse the importance of the asparagine residue in position 5 of oxytocin, 5[α,γ diamino butyric] oxytocin was also synthesized. The nona peptides were prepared stepwise using the *p*. nitrophenyl ester method by scheme 1 for synthesis of 4 (α,γ diamino butyric) oxytocin, and by scheme 2 for synthesis of 5 (α,γ diamino butyric) oxytocin. The structure of nona peptides (IV, IX) was confirmed by its analytical data and by amino acid analysis after hydrolysis with 6 *N* HCl at 110° for about 22 hr. Final removal of protecting groups from the nona peptides amide was carried out at 0° for 30 min. in HF^5 , the compound (100 mg) was dissolved in trifluoro acetic acid (0.5 ml) together with anisole (0.08 ml) before treatment with HF. (5 ml). After the reaction, HF was removed under vacuum, and the reaction product was taken up into 100 ml of water. The solution was adjusted to pH 6.7 with ammonia, and carbon dioxide-free air was bubbled through the solution for about 2hr. and some biological testings are under consideration.

Scheme (1) for synthesis of 4 [α,γ diamino butyric] oxytocin.

Scheme (2) for synthesis of 5 [α , γ diamino butyric] oxytocin.

Experimental

The time allowed for the completion of the reaction and the purity of the prepared compounds was controlled by means of thin layer chromatography (T. L. C.) using freshly prepared solvent (butanol : water : acetic acid 62 : 26 : 12). The N-benzyloxycarbonyl amino acids and peptides were detected by ninhydrin spray on chromatograms after treating with hydrogen bromide in acetic acid at room temperature (20°) for 1 hr. Melting points were uncorrected.

General method for preparation of peptides :

To N-benzyloxycarbonyl-peptide amide (1 mol) in acetic acid (2.25 ml) was added hydrogen bromide in acetic acid (1.8 ml). After being allowed to stand for one hour at room temperature dry ether (100 ml) was added. The precipitated hydrobromide was washed with ether (10 ml) and dried over NaOH. The solid mass was dissolved in the least amount of dimethyl formamide and triethylamine (1 mol) was added followed by benzyloxycarbonyl amino acid *p*-nitrophenyl ester⁶⁻⁸ (1 mol). After being left for 18 hr. at room temperature the solid mass was treated with ethyl acetate (70 ml), filtered, washed with 2NHCl, 5. NaHCO₃, water, ether, and recrystallized from ethyl acetate.

α -Z- γ -TOS-L-Dab-L-Asp(NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (I) : m. p. 160°-62°, R_F 0.47 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -47° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 57.03; H, 6.35; N, 13.20 ; C₄₆H₆₉N₉O₁₀S₂ requires C, 57.26 ; H, 6.43 ; N, 13.07%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (II) : m. p. 190°-95° ; R_F 0.52 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -53° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 57.81 ; H, 6.62 ; N, 12.91 ; C₅₃H₇₃N₁₀O₁₁S₂ requires C, 57.93 ; H, 6.77 ; N, 13.00%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (III) : m. p. 220°-23° ; R_F 0.57 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -61° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (found : C, 58.88, H, 6.45 ; N, 12.30 ; C₆₁H₈₂N₁₁O₁₃S₂ requires C, 59.00 ; H, 6.61 ; N, 12.42%).

Z-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Asp (NH₂)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (IV) : m. p. 236°-39°, R_F 0.65 [α]_D²⁰ = -70° (C=1, in D. M. F.) (found C, 59.34 ; H, 6.35 ; N, 11.65 ; C₇₁H₉₃N₁₂O₁₄S₃ requires C, 59.45 ; H, 6.49, N, 11.72%). Amino acid analysis : Cystiene 1.92 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.91 (1 mol), iso-leucine 1.02 (1, mol, α , γ Diamino butyric 0.99 (1 mol), aspartic acid 1.01 (1 mol), proline 0.98 (1 mol), leucine 1.02 (1 mol), and glycine 1.0 (1 mol).

α -Z- γ -Tos-L-Dab-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (V) : m. p. 155°-57°, R_F 0.49 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -59° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 59.25 ; H, 6.49 ; N, 11.35 ; C₄₂H₅₆N₇O₈S, requires C, 59.41 ; H, 6.60 ; N, 11.53%).

Z-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (VI) : m. p. 179-82°, R_F 0.54 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -64° (C=1, in D. M. F.), (Found : C, 57.53 ; H, 6.35 ; N, 12.71 ; C₄₇H₆₄N₈O₁₀S₂ requires C, 57.65 ; H, 6.54 ; N, 12.88%).

Z-L-Ileu-L-Glu(NH₂)-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Cys(BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (VII) : m. p. 190°-92°, R_F 0.59, [α]_D²⁰ = -67° (C=1, in D. M. F.) (Found : C, 58.13 ; H, 6.45 ; N, 12.71 ; C₅₃H₇₅N₁₀O₁₁S₂ requires C, 58.29 ; H, 6.77 ; N, 12.83%).

Z-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu (NH₂)-L-Dab (Tos)-L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ (VIII) : m. p. 213°-16°, R_F 0.63 ; [α]_D²⁰ = -76° (C=1, in D. M. F.) (Found : C, 59.20 ; H, 6.55 ; N, 12.43 ; C₆₂H₈₄N₁₁O₁₃S₂ requires C, 59.33 ; H, 6.69 ; N, 12.58%).

Z-L-Cys(BZ)-L-Tyr-L-Ileu-L-Glu(NH₂)-L-Dab(Tos)
L-Cys (BZ)-L-Pro-L-Leu-Gly NH₂ IX : m. p. 227°-29°, R_F 0.1 ; $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -80^\circ$ (C=1, in D. M. F.),
 (Found : C, 59.53 ; H, 6.41 ; N, 11.49 : C₇₂H₉₅N₁₂O₁₄S₃ requires C, 59.70 ; H, 6.55 ; N, 11.61%). Amino acid analysis : Cystiene 1.96 (2 mol), tyrosine 0.95 (1 mol), iso-leucine 1.02 (1 mol), glutamic acid 0.99 (1 mol), α , γ diamino butyric acid 1.00 (1 mol), proline 0.97 (1 mol), leucine 1.02 (1 mol), and glycine 1.00 (1 mol).

References

1. a. R. WALTER, and I. I. SCHWARTZ, *J. Biol. Chem.* 1966, **241**, 5500.
- b. V. DU VIGNEAUD, G. FLOURFT, and R. WALTER, *J. Biol. Chem.* 1966, **241**, 2093.
2. St. GUTTMANN, and R. A. BOISSONNAS, *Helv. Chim. Acta.* 1963, **46**, 1626.
3. F. MOREL, and P. BASTIDE, in "Symposium on Oxytocin, Vasopressin and their Structural Analogues". Ed. J. Rudinger, Pergamon Press, New York NY, 1964, p. 47.
4. I. PHOTAKI, and V. DU VIGNEAUD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1965, **87**, 908.
5. S. SAKAKIBARA and J. SHIMONISHI; "Peptides", North-Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1967, p. 44.
6. J. RUDINGER, "Pure and Applied Chemistry", 1963 ; **7**, p. 325.
7. M. BODANSZKY and V. DU VIGNEAUD, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1959, **81**, 5688.
8. M. BODANSZKY, *Nature* 1955, **175**, 685, *Acta Chim. Acad Sci Hung.* 1957, **10**, 335.